

The Relationship between Sociological Factors and Compulsive Buying Behavior: Mediating Effect of Materialism

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Abstract:

The key objective of this research study is to find the relationship between Sociological factors (that includes Peer group, Media Celebrity endorsement, TV advertisement, and Family communication) and Compulsive buying behavior with mediating factor Materialism. Previous studies have shown that there is a positive impact of all sociological factors on compulsive buying behavior. 92% responses among questionnaire were usable. The reliability analysis, correlation, regression, and other test the ts were performed through SPSS. This study suggested that sociological factors enhance the compulsive buying behavior. The consequences of the findings of the study reveal that there is a significant positive relation of all factors on compulsive buying behavior. Future Studies can be done with other factors like age, psychological factors, personal factors, demographic factors, and occupational factors

Keywords: Sociological Factors, Compulsive Buying Behavior, Materialism

Introduction & Background of Study

Self-expressiveness in shopping is defined that how much a consumer thinks that a shopping activity is important for his self-esteem. It is influenced by his experience in shopping activities, the potential of recognition through shopping, and effort used (Joseph Sirgy et al. 2016). Materialism is defined as it is the preoccupation of the material world. High materialism is a situation in which a person seeks pleasure from external things such as money, status, and appearance. Be that as it may, Materialism, as a kind of extraneous motivation, may range service all the fulfillment of mental needs, and afterward debilitates individual prosperity (Rong et al. 2017) Parental materialism and child materialism has the positive relationship. Guardians don't know about the negative worries of materialism on their kids. Results demonstrated that lion's share of youngsters and guardians imagine that achievement is ownership of material things. It was likewise uncovered that the larger part of guardians and youngsters connect accomplishment with ownership of material things (Bassiouny & Noha 2012) there is a positive effect of best friend's adaptive strategies on the change of adaptive strategies of youngsters. While Best friends' adaptive strategies for sadness did not have an effect on youngsters' adaptive strategies (Reindl, Gniewosz & Reinders 2016). The consumer culture is a culture, in which the consumers will consume and display goods and services for nonfunctional reasons, such as status and pleasure seeking (Müller & de Zwaan 2004). For over three decades Compulsive buying has become one of the most important components of consumer culture, and has been of interest to consumer behavior, researchers and government authorities, not only in the developed countries but also in developing countries (D et al., 2014) *Compulsive buying* is defined as recurrent obsession with *buying* or impulses to *buy* that are experienced as tantalizing, invasive, and/or ridiculous. The *buying* behavior causes marked distress, interferes with social functioning and marriage and often results in financial problems. Compulsive buying behavior repeatedly forces the consumer to buy, in order to bring a momentary relaxation from mental stress, etc. (Hultman et al. 2015) Compulsive buying behavior results in many negatives economic, social and psychological consequences. despite of the fact that compulsive buyers have huge debts and already occupied the things they continue to buy same things resulting in increasing number of items (Islam et al .2017) Compulsive buyers typically feel unhappiness, guilt, shame, or embarrassment due to their buying behavior (R et al . 2017) Quantities of research papers squeeze articles and books allude to compulsive buying and to the issues it might cause and all these influence compulsives buying contemporary to concern (Benson 2000) Examines show that around 5.8 % (Koran et al. 2006) or 8.9 % compulsive buying, failure to control the buying conduct has been as of late

concentrated widely; notwithstanding, few investigations have been directed in Pakistan. Consumers have diverse purchasing practices as a result of their unique arrangements of needs, needs and want. The purchasing behaviors are settled upon the blend of social, cultural, psychological and environmental factors. In this study, social components are underlined expressly which may influence the conduct of consumers that can prompt compulsivity in regards to buys. The people usually follow up on the drive or urge which can increment coordinate changes face to face's purchasing conduct. Along these lines issue in requiring, control can prompt unfavorable outcomes, for example, addiction (Małgorzata et al. 2016). This research seeks to determine what makes young adults materialistic. The study examines the mediating role of materialism between the contextual factors and compulsive buying. Data was gathered from Pakistani university students. Partial Least Square (PLS) technique was used to analyze the data.

Problem Statement

Individuals gain materialistic principles in the course of social learning from relatives, peers, television, and social media, all of which are often supportive of a materialistic way of life (Sheldon, et al., 2004). The growing number of excessive buying behaviors among young adults is the cause of materialism and compulsive buying (Islam, et al., 2017)Thence, the purpose of this research is to reveal & provide the relationship between sociological factors on compulsive buying behavior with adequate enlightenment to materialism.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Compulsive Buying

The subject of compulsive buying behavior has gotten impressive consideration from analysts (Hultman et al. 2015) characterized compulsive buying as "a constant anomalous type of shopping and spending portrayed by the extraordinary, wild, and dull inclination to purchase, ignoring the results. Research has depicted compulsive buying behavior as a psychological state in which a disconnected person who needs motivation control and has low self-esteem joined with anxiety and Materialism looks for fervor as indicated by (Dittmar & Drury, 2000) enthusiastic purchasers trust that costly material is fundamental for bliss and achievement substantially more than typical purchasers trust this. Specialists summed up those large amounts of urgent purchasing conduct might be produced from materialism, peer communication, television advertisements, and media exposure (Dittmar & Hower, 2005). Factors, for example, the last three are considered in the present work as precursors of materialism. Dittmar and Drury (2000) recommended grown-ups who have a huge propensity toward materialism are additionally liable to display compulsive buying behavior prompting uncontrolled purchasing, and this relationship is a focal point of this present paper. Compulsive buying disorder (CBD) is portrayed by extreme shopping insights and purchasing conduct that prompts trouble or impedance. Subjects with CBD report a distraction with shopping, repurchase strain or tension, and a liberating sensation following the buy. Dark (2007) Compulsive buying disorder (CBD) is described by inordinate shopping discernments and purchasing conduct that prompts misery or weakness. Granero, et al. (2016). Research on the topic of compulsive buying was started by the mid of 1980's, but in 1972 Tauber already investigated the individual's shopping motivation. He found that people buy the goods only for need but for pleasure seeking when they get bored or depressed and for social communication when they feel alone. Prior investigations on compulsive buying are limited to basic articles (Kaufman, 1976) few reports in the noticeable press) summed up the purchaser's benevolent which was being examined by Tauber. Furthermore, it was affirmed that while Materialism and mental misery side effects would speak to helplessness determinants expanding the affinity for habitual purchasing, the high scores in life fulfillment would act to diminish the probability of turning into an enthusiastic purchaser. Likewise, our outcomes proposed that aversion and mediation endeavors in connection with compulsive buying among youngsters ought to incorporate particular segments went for the diminishment of the significance doled out to cash and belonging, and also at the relief of psychological distress symptoms (Villardefrancos & Otero-López, 2016).

Peer group and Materialism

Research has built up that youths who frequently compare with their peers are slanted to surrender to peer pressure and are more materialistic than the individuals who don't have a strong peer-group association (Benmoyal-Bouzaglo & Moschis, 2010). Kids and adolescents find out about social standards, culture, and how to carry on specifically circumstances from multiple points of view (Korgaonkar & Moschis, 1987). An overview led on young people in China found a huge connection between peer contact, the inclination to peer pressure, and materialism (Naomi, et al., 2016) Peers are more persuasive than guardians in the reception of materialistic behavior (Chaplin & John, 2010). The relationship between materialism and peer relations are probably going to exist in primary school kids yet have not been examined beforehand. Companion dismissal is identified with higher seen peer culture weight, which thus is related to more prominent materialism. The underwriting of social thought processes in materialism intervenes the connection between perceived peer pressure and materialism. Banerjee and Dittmar (2008) In a study with 12-18 year-olds, self-esteem mediates the relationship between parent/peer influence and adolescent materialism Chaplin and John (2010). People or families regularly have some degree for the decision of peer groups, regardless of whether through the choice of the neighborhood of residence, school, or companions. Peer group pressure prompts elevated amounts of materialism, maybe on the grounds that companion acknowledgment is viewed as the ideal approach to pick up the certainty and dear friendship of one's peers in a particular community (Isaksen & Roper, 2012). Comprehensive social assessment theory demonstrates that individuals assess themselves against others by personal material possessions to set up their social standing (Motl et al. 2002). High peer group pressure increases materialism among young adults (Moschis, 2010). Based on a review of the literature, this subsequent hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Young adults who are highly influenced by their peers are more materialistic than those who are less influenced

The Influence of Media Celebrity Endorsements on Materialism

Celebrity worship is a worldwide phenomenon among teenagers, and young consumers (Yue & Cheung, 2000) and celebrity admiration are basic in networks of youth around the globe. Roughly 20 percent of all ads overall utilize well-known personalities as spokespersons (Shimp & Andrews, 2013). Search good (shoes) supported by a celebrity in a commercial evoked altogether more consideration, want, and activity from the buyer than completed an online client survey. We additionally found that online client audits developed higher than the big name underwriting on the size of members' memory, pursuit and offer states of mind toward the experience great (Wei & Lu, 2013). A big name's general credibility, and in addition aptitude, is impacted by the apparent state of mind toward a marked item. Furthermore, an inadequately saw brand might likewise impact a superstar's appeal and reliability adversely. Be that as it may, it was discovered that an emphatically saw mark does not really build similar traits of appeal and dependability on a less respected celebrity (Doss, 2011). Total celebrity media diet regimen was likewise altogether identified with materialism. Discoveries recommend that a media eat fewer crabs high in VIP culture and way of life has a critical effect on rising grown-ups' distraction with consumerism, especially for ladies. This exploration adds to a developing assortment of writing on the impacts of a superstar soaked media condition and the development of materialistic attitudes (Lewallen, Miller & Behm-Morawitz, 2016). The present research asked additionally concentrates to be carried on to look at the explanations for the powerlessness of utilizing big names to impact customers' purchasing decision and product choice (Pughazhendi, Ravindran & Sudharani, 2012). Therefore, we hypothesize:

H2: Young adults who report a greater tendency to imitate celebrities are more materialistic than those with a lower tendency to imitate celebrities.

Influence of TV Advertising on Materialism

Research has revealed that TV advertisements stimulate materialism among young adults (Dittmar et al., 2014). As indicated by the past literature, advertisements have emphatically affected materialism since it is proposed to

fortify a longing for organization items (Yang & Ganahl, 2004). Sitting in front of the TV is straightforwardly connected to materialism among young people (Chan, 2003) found there is a positive connection between one's disposition towards TV advertisement and materialism. Also, customer conduct analysts have suggested a causal connection between TV and materialism (Zinkhan & Pereira, 1994). The report exhibits the primary investigation to address assumption toward advertising, materialism, and vanity in the globalized city of Dubai. A reasonable model is created and consequent speculations are tried through auxiliary condition demonstrating. The primary research discoveries propose that customers in Dubai display positive perceptions of advertising as well as higher levels of materialism and vanity. Notion toward advertising is found to decidedly impact materialism levels, while materialism unequivocally impacts sees, worry for physical appearance, and individual accomplishment. Feeling toward advertising, in any case, has no immediate impact on any vanity characteristic, recommending that vanity is progressively an inside individual quality (Mady et al., 2011). These results provide evidence that self-construal and materialism contribute to social media use independent of nationality. Theoretical and managerial implications for international advertising strategies are discussed. Chu, Windels and Kamal (2016) In this investigation, we propose a hypothetical structure through which we inspect the direct and the roundabout impacts of advertising on college students' materialistic attitudes. The structure is based because of-assumed impact display, which enables us to look at how advertising and peer interface with each other and apply joint impacts. Hence, it can be inferred that TV promoting is influencing kids by expanding their nourishment utilization design, inclination for low supplement, high in sugar, fat and salt (SFS) sustenance's and drinks, change in demeanor that is forceful in nature and tendency towards unnecessary (Latif & Abideen, 2011) TV advertisements aim at creating a culture that encourages the audience to seek success, happiness, status, and popularity as well as embracing social stereotypes (Buijzen, 2012) conducted a study of adolescents and found that TV advertisements have both short and long-term effects on materialistic values. Based on these findings, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Young adults who watch more television advertisements will be more materialistic than those who watch fewer televisions advertisements.

The Influence of Family Communication on Materialism

Research has revealed that socio-oriented family communication style leads to the development of materialistic orientations (Moschis, 1987) they propose that the socio-oriented family communication environment that anxieties adjustment to social standards and the significance of passing judgment on others as people in view of their consumption habits advance the significance of symbolic consumption and prompts the improvement of materialistic values (Gwin et al., 2005). Our underlying investigation into this zone finds that youthful grown-ups raised in disrupted families are more materialistic and display larger amounts of compulsive consumption than youthful grown-ups raised in unblemished families. Moreover, we demonstrate that the between family structure and compulsive consumption is somewhat interceded by both the measure of assets accessible inside the family and the level of family pressure. Variables measured included: recall of ads, attitudes toward TV ads, materialism, effects of ads on buying, exposure to TV and magazines, family communication about consumption, social utility reasons, communication utility reasons, and various consumption reasons. A comparison of results, between younger and older students, indicate no significant differences in the learning variables, but does show differences on nearly all communication variable. By and large, family communication forms, and also youngster's age, impact both the immediate and roundabout acquiring intensity of kids. Idea situated communication, which urges youngsters to build up an autonomous utilization point of view, expands the immediate and backhanded obtaining impact of kids. Socio-oriented communication, which urges yielding to parental gauges, is identified with expanded utilization reliance (Rose, Boush & Shoham, 2002). The debilitating of parent-child bonds as a diminishment in elusive assets and in addition decrease in material resources accessible to the child because of family disruptions (Moschis, Mathur, Fatt & Pizzutti, 2013) found a negative relationship between emotional family resources and socio-oriented family communication, which in turn predicts materialism. Therefore, we hypothesize:

H4: Young adults who are highly influenced by their family communication are more materialistic than those who are less influenced.

Materialism

Most recent four decades, examines have discovered that expanding part of materialism has turned into a central construct of the consumer behavior (Arndt, 2004) have talked about materialism theoretically as an inert build. As indicated by Belk (1988) materialism is a huge use design, as youngsters as often as possible utilize material possessions to pass on their expanded selves. Belk (1984) clarifies materialism as a phase in which a man thinks certain material goods are required for pleasure throughout everyday life (Richins & Dawson, 1992) The present study measures the materialism by using the materialism value scale approach in (Tahir et al, 2017). They utilize sumptuous items as a standard to imply the social position, status, and achievement. Materialism increments from center youth to early youthfulness and decreases from ahead of schedule to late puberty. Age contrasts are intervened by changes in confidence happening from center youth through youthfulness.

Materialism and Compulsive Buying Behavior

Materialism can be defined as “the degree to which people endeavor to take part in the development and support of the self through the obtaining and utilization of products, services, and experience” (Shrum et al. 2013) Individuals with high materialistic values want more elevated amounts of status and need to have costly things as an approach to enable them to accomplish real life objectives (Halliwell et al., 2005).Materialism is a steady indicator of compulsive buying behavior (Dittmar, Bond, Hurst & Kasser, 2014) .A number of scholars Burroughs (2009) have found that compulsive buying is a blend of low drive control and an abnormal state of materialism, where purchaser merchandise assume a noteworthy enthusiastic part in a person's life (Dittmar, 2005) to such an extent that he or she purchases things just to connect with material goods Compulsive buying has a solid association with money, social image, and possession (Steketee & Williams, 2002) recommending that acquisitions and possessions are vital facets of compulsive buying. Therefore, we hypothesize:

H5: Materialism is positively related to compulsive buying in youth.

Mediating effect of Materialism

This research seeks to determine whether materialism acts as a mediator between certain sociological factors and compulsive buying. A number of studies have provided the theoretical background for the mediation effect of materialism on compulsive behavior. Davis (2011) tested peer communication empirically as a mediator between the independent variables (gender and family) and the dependent variables (materialism and compulsive behavior). Monroe (2008) investigated materialism as a predictor of compulsive buying behavior. Scholars have extensively discussed how sociological factors like peer pressure, media celebrity endorsements, and television advertisement are related to materialism and compulsive buying among adults (Dittmar, 2005). Based on the extant literature, we propose that materialism plays a mediating role between the sociological factors of peer pressure, media celebrity endorsements, television advertisements and compulsive behavior. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: Materialism mediates the relationship between the sociological factors peer pressure, media celebrity endorsements, television advertisements, and Family communication and compulsive buying behavior.

Figure2.1: Model of Research

Sample and Data Collection

The target population for the data collection is HEC recognized universities in Punjab Pakistan. Total 61 Universities are targeted. Random sampling will be used as a sampling technique.

City	Public University	Private University	Total
Lahore	14	20	34
Rawalpindi	5	2	7
Gujranwala		1	1
Multan	5	1	6
Dera Ghazi Khan	1		1
Faisalabad	4	1	5
Sialkot	1	1	2
Bahawalpur	2		2
Rahim Yar Khan	1		1
Gujrat	1		1
Sargodha	1		1
Total	35	26	61

Demographical Statistics

Respondents were asked about certain demographics i.e. gender, age, and region (see Table 4.1). Majority of the respondents were male (i.e. N = 156, 56.6 %), while 43.5 % were female. On the basis of age, 50.0 percent (N = 137) were between 20-22 years and 35 percent (N = 96) were between 22-24 years.

Demographical Characteristics of Respondents

Demographics (n=276)		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	156	56.5
	Female	120	43.5
Age	20-22 Years	137	49.6
	22-24 Years	96	34.8
	24-26 Years	43	15.6
	Above 26	50	18.1
	Total	276	100.0

Data Normality Assessment

The prior assumptions of running structural equation model and other confirmatory factor includes that data should be normally distributed. Several tests can be run for checking the normality of the data. However, commonly used test for data normality assessment researchers usually goes for Kurtosis and Skewness. The descriptive analysis employed to know the results of Kurtosis and Skewness for all variables. There are two assumptions regarding values for Kurtosis and Skewness. However, the values for Skewness should be in between +3 to -3 and values for Kurtosis should be less than +10 to -10. Results reveal that all variables are normally distributed. Table values for Kurtosis and Skewness are in between -1 to +1. However, negative values resulted in Skewness and Kurtosis. Tables for Skewness and Kurtosis are given in Appendix

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
MCD	276	2.5634	1.09713	.576	.147	-1.246	.292
TVA	276	2.5562	.92443	.392	.147	-1.343	.292
M	276	2.1101	.91200	1.950	.147	2.622	.292
CBB	276	1.9833	.79188	1.880	.147	2.544	.292
FC	276	1.9203	1.02202	1.718	.147	1.978	.292
Valid (list wise)	N 276						

Reliability of Variables

Reliability of the instrument is measured by the most commonly used test of Cronbatch Alpha (Ayes, 1998). Bair et. al (1995) claimed that the range of acceptability index of Cronbatch Alpha is .6 to .9. Pallant

(2000) put the same annotations on the goodness index of Cronbach Alpha as the coefficient value of alpha ranges from 0 to 1. Henceforth, Vellis (1991) claimed that the coefficient of Cronbach Alpha is associated with the internal excellence of the contents of the variable. Sekaran, (2000) categorized the Cronbach Alpha coefficient excellence degrees and suggested that the coefficient value of reliability less than 0.6 are inadequate, values within the range of 0.7 are taken on a satisfactory level where as the values till 0.8 are good and 0.9 are taken as excellent. This categorization shows that the values near to 1 are more close to the excellence. This range among the internal excellence of factors facilitates the credibility as well as provides the assistance in ascertaining the relationship among the factors/contents of the variables.

Reliability Analysis

Name of the Factor	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
Peer Group Communication	0.884	3
Media Celebrities Endorsement	0.829	4
TV Advertisement	0.662	4
Materialism	0.902	5
Compulsive Buying Behavior	0.793	5
Family Communication	0.871	2
Total	0.890	29

Pearson' Correlation

Correlation is the extent to which two or more variables are related to each other (Sekaran, 2003). Correlation determines the strength of the relationship between dependent and independent variables. It also tells to what extent variables are strongly paired with each other. One of the best and most common techniques used for correlation is Pearson, which is also used in this study. The correlation value between .3 to.5 is considered to be moderately correlated whereas .5 to .7 is considered to be strongly correlated whereas the (Sig. < .01).

Correlations

		PGC	MCD	TVA	M	CBB	FC
PGC	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N	276					
MCD	Pearson Correlation	.057	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.349					
	N	276	276				
TVA	Pearson Correlation	.142*	.884***	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.019	.000				

	N	276	276	276		
M	Pearson Correlation	.703**	-.196**	-.048	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001	.430		
	N	276	276	276	276	
CBB	Pearson Correlation	.666**	-.194**	-.046	.853**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001	.450	.000	
	N	276	276	276	276	276
FC	Pearson Correlation	.013	.063	.062	-.048	.157**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.827	.295	.301	.428	.009
	N	276	276	276	276	276

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.5 Regression Analysis

The adjusted R square value explains the change in the dependent variable due to independent variables. The adjusted R Square value is .536 which means that 54% change can be occurred in dependent variables due to change in independent variables.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.737 ^a	.543	.536	.53919

a. Predictors: (Constant), PGC, FC, MCD, TVA

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.962	.123		7.804	.000
	PGC	.480	.031	.650	15.504	.000
	MCD	-.365	.064	-.506	-5.693	.000
	TVA	.256	.077	.299	3.341	.001
	FC	.125	.032	.161	3.918	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CBB

beta value for the peer group is 0.659, which shows a strong positive significant impact on compulsive buying behavior, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for media celebrity endorsements is -0.506, which shows a strong negative significant impact on compulsive buying behavior, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for TV advertisement is 0.299, which shows a moderate positive significant impact on compulsive buying behavior, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for family communication is 0.161, which shows a weak positive significant impact on compulsive buying behavior, whereas the (Sig. < .05).

Mediation

The adjusted R square value explains the change in the dependent variable due to independent variables. The adjusted R Square value is .774 which means that 77% change can be occurred in dependent variables due to change in independent variables.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.882 ^a	.779	.774	.37608

a. Predictors: (Constant), M, TVA, FC, PGC, MCD

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.192	.097		1.975	.049
	PGC	.103	.031	.140	3.337	.001
	MCD	-.106	.047	-.146	-2.236	.026
	TVA	.075	.055	.087	1.366	.173
	FC	.150	.022	.194	6.741	.000
	M	.642	.038	.739	16.943	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CBB

Partial mediation has been found among all independent variables except TV advertisement and dependent variable. There is full mediation found between TV advertisement and compulsive buying behavior.

Discussion

Based on the extant literature Cole et al (2015) we divided our conceptual framework into two models. In the first model, four significant facets: peer groups, media celebrity endorsement, TV advertisements and Family Communication were analyzed. With the second model, we examined the effect of materialism on compulsive buying behavior among young adults. The results of this study supported our hypotheses, confirming that materialism is one of the primary causes of compulsive buying behavior among young adults. The findings of this study are in accordance with the extant literature (Chan et al., 2006) the results indicated that peer group pressure is helping to arouse the materialistic values and compulsive buying behavior among young adults. Pakistani youth have a strong aspiration for material possession. In Pakistan, as in other countries, there is a strong link between possessions and friendships, because those young adults who engage significantly with peers are more materialistic than those who do not (Chan, 2003). This result confirms that young adults who are involved in peer groups experience pressure to comply with their friends' suggestions while shopping. In the learning and working environments young individuals also receive influence from their peers, which affects their materialistic attitudes. According to the social exchange theory, young adults are inclined to evaluate their material possessions with their friends. The results in the Pakistani context are positive in this aspect and in accord with past studies (Chan & Prendergast, 2007), La Ferle and Chan (2008). Looking at hypothesis H3, TV advertisement seems to have the propensity to influence the development of materialistic behavior among

young adults in Pakistan. TV affects people's perception, so those who are watching television very frequently are more materialistic. Due to the tendency toward high materialistic values, the past literature supported that high materialistic values may impact greatly the compulsive buying level. As youth became a huge market segment for multinational companies for promoting brands, companies have allocated heavy budgets for advertising campaigns. Advertisements often persuade viewers to spend by using imagery of nice-looking or well-known consumers who use the product, by indicating a societal incentive for consuming the product, and by relating the product to those who are well off (Sheldon et al., 2004). Previous findings suggested high exposure to TV advertisements can lead towards high materialistic values (La Ferle & Chan., 2008) and the current survey confirms that is valid in Pakistan also. The media celebrity effect was found to be a stronger predictor of materialism as compared to peer group and media exposure, which means celebrities have more effect on building materialistic values in Pakistan. Youth always have idealized media celebrities so celebrities in advertising appeal to customers as well as those who have never tried the brand. Celebrities demonstrate their wealth to the audience through expensive products (Chan & Zhang , 2007) and this can lead to compulsive buying and overspending among those who idolize the celebrities. Pakistani society is undergoing cultural change. The following features are responsible for these changes: High increase in the middle-class group, expansion of mass media (TV, radio, and social media), and technological innovations. The society has been reacting against these cultural changes, but no segment of life has been free from the effect of these changes. The following changes can be observed as a result of the cultural transformation. First, a numerical increase in the middle-class income group has changed. The overall consumption habits of the society. Today, young adults are highly concerned about material possessions and obtaining expensive things as this appears to be a significant factor in modern life. As a result, the family system is also in transition and moving from collectivism to individualism. The basic reason is the high proportion of young adults. Second, mass media has also influenced the individual lifestyle. Media has played an important role in shaping behaviors, and youth is strongly influenced by media. Media use is incorporated as a control variable in this research, as media use increases materialistic behavior among young adults.

Conclusion:

Pakistan is an emerging country that is passing through cultural and social changes, and the reason behind this change is the immense usage of social media among the country's youth. In Pakistan, young adults use media for many purposes, including collecting information about products, brands, and discounts, and today's youth have greater media exposure (i.e., Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn) than the youth of the past (Lee, Jolles & Krabbendam, 2016). The present research examines the relationship between Sociological factors and Compulsive buying behavior with the mediating effect of Materialism among young adults in Pakistan, and found that Pakistani young adults are exhibiting high materialistic values. The findings can provide valuable inputs for further understanding of the Pakistani market and Pakistani consumers. This has had a significant influence on the materialistic values and compulsive buying. Therefore, this empirical research reported herein gives insight into these factors and also indicates that young adults in modern Islamic culture (Pakistan) are remarkably similar to those in other cultures in their materialistic outlooks. Finally, from the research findings, it is concluded that our study variables (Peer group, Media celebrities, TV advertisement and Family communication) are primary causes of materialism and compulsive buying among young adults of Pakistan. Materialism mediated relationship between the study variables, representing sociological factors, and compulsive buying.

Limitations and Future Research

Our study has several limitations. First, we gathered data from respondents who were all university students. The results of this model could be different in other environments, so the study findings have limited external validity; the results of this study might differ with a different target audience. Future researchers should retest the conceptual model and validate it in other contexts as well. Second, the data was collected from the cities of province Punjab where young people are more affected by contextual factors (peer group, media celebrity endorsement, and TV advertisement) as compared to the rural area residents. Thus, the study findings are limited to metropolitan cities. Future research should focus on large sample size and collecting data from across

the country because that would help to get a more comprehensive view of young adult attitudes towards the study constructs. Third, our research used cross-sectional data. Behavior changes over time, and compulsive buying behavior is not a one-dimensional construct, so a longitudinal study could help to clarify this concept. Fourth, further study should also consider the type of products (luxury vs. inexpensive) as a predictor variable of materialism and compulsive buying.

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